

INFLUENCE OF TOURIST TRAVEL EXPERIENCE DIMENSIONS ON ENVIRONMENTAL COMPETENCE

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ABSTRACT

Tourism is a significant global industry, with the potential to influence environmental outcomes on sustainable tourism practices. This quantitative study investigates the influence of tourists' travel experience dimensions on their environmental competence, focusing on perceived value and satisfaction, guided by the Theory of Planned Behavior. A questionnaire adapted from Bhutto et al. was used as the data-gathering instrument to obtain the needed information of this study. The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design. Data were collected and analyzed from 100 participants to determine their assessments of travel experiences and environmental competencies. Results reveal that participants gave high ratings to their travel experiences, with high means for perceived value and satisfaction. Additionally, participants demonstrated high levels of environmental awareness and engagement in sustainable practices. Regression analysis indicated a significant influence of perceived value and satisfaction on environmental competence. These findings underscore the importance of enhancing perceived value and satisfaction in travel experiences to foster greater environmental competence among tourists, highlighting the need for sustainable tourism practices and environmental education initiatives. This study contributes valuable insights for policymakers, destination managers, and stakeholders in developing strategies for promoting responsible and sustainable tourism. Furthermore, the study emphasizes the importance of addressing tourists' concerns about pricing and actively engaging them in environmental conservation activities during their travels. The analysis suggests a strong connection between tourists' perceptions of their travel experiences and their environmental competence, reinforcing the potential for interventions targeting these dimensions to promote sustainable behaviors.

Keywords: *engagement, environment, satisfaction, sustainable, tourist, travel, value*

INTRODUCTION

In 2019, the Philippine Statistics Authority reported that tourism contributed 12.7% to the country's Gross Domestic Product. As of 2023, the industry is gradually recovering from the catastrophic event caused by the COVID-19 virus. This recovery entails a significant growth of ecotourism industry, which has been historically a major source of employment and integral component for economic development.

Ecotourism, a growing trend of tourism, emphasizes environmental conservation while focusing on experiencing nature and natural landscapes. This study, anchored by Bjork (2007), notes that phenomena such as climate change have heightened awareness about environmental conservation, giving rise to ecotourism as a new opportunity within the travel business. Ecotourism emphasizes the natural conservation of tourist locations, thereby, increasing tourists' environmental concern. These tourists are expected to adhere to local legislation and engage in ecologically responsible practices to avoid harming the natural environment.

The Philippines, with its rich cultural heritage and breath taking natural landscapes, has long been a favored destination for domestic and international tourists. However, the rapid growth of tourism in the country has raised concerns about its environmental impact. Issues such as beach erosion, pollution, habitat degradation, and water scarcity have become prevalent (Parducho, 2015). Amidst these environmental challenges, tourists in the Philippine context play a critical role in shaping the sustainability of their travel experiences. Understanding how various dimensions of tourists' travel experiences influence their environmental competence is imperative for promoting responsible tourism and preserving the country's unique natural and cultural assets.

Despite the notable correlations found between environmental attitudes and environmental behavior (Wang, 2016), there is still a need to delve into understanding how specific dimensions of tourists' travel experience dimensions influence their environmental competence in the Philippine context. This research is of paramount importance for the Philippines as it offers insights into crafting effective strategies to balance tourism development with environmental preservation. Towards this end, this study was conceptualized.

Framework

The study assumes that tourist travel experience dimensions can impact individuals' environmental competence. By examining the relationships between these independent variables such as tourist travel experience dimensions and the dependent variable composed of environmental competence, the framework provides a basis for understanding the factors that can influence individuals' engagement in environmental awareness and sustainable practices. This knowledge can help guide strategies and interventions to promote sustainable behaviors and enhance environmental conservation efforts.

This assumption is grounded in the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), which provides a well-established framework for understanding how individuals' attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control influence their intentions and subsequently their behavior. The TPB, developed by Icek Ajzen in the late 1990s, has been widely used in various fields to predict and explain human behavior. It posits that an individual's intention to engage in a specific behavior. In this case, demonstrating environmental competence is the key determinant of whether they actually performs such behavior or not. This research draws on the Theory of Planned Behavior to investigate how tourists' travel experience dimensions, including perceived value, and satisfaction, influence their environmental competence, as reflected in environmental awareness and sustainable practices.

By applying this theoretical framework, the study seeks to provide valuable insights into promoting sustainable tourism practices and mitigating the environmental influences of tourism in the selected context. In this study, TPB is applied in the context of tourism, focusing on tourists' environmental competence with environmental awareness and sustainable practices as the key variables such as the three travel experience dimensions: perceived value, involvement, and satisfaction, as the independent variables.

Perceived value, a component of tourist travel experience, refers to the perceived benefits or utility that tourists expect to gain from their travel experiences. This can encompass factors like the quality of services, enjoyment, and the overall travel experience. In this study, perceived value serves as one of the independent variables. It hypothesizes that tourists who perceive greater value in sustainable tourism practices are more likely to exhibit environmental competence.

Similarly, Nguyen and Mattila (2018) reported that perceived value significantly influences environmental competence. When individuals perceive intrinsic value in the environment, recognize personal benefits, align with social norms, understand long-term consequences, and are educated about environmental issues, they are more likely to engage in behaviors that promote sustainability and reduce their environmental footprint.

Tourist satisfaction is the second component of tourist travel experience, measuring how well the actual travel experience meets or exceeds expectations. Satisfied tourists are more likely to develop positive attitudes and intentions towards environmentally responsible behaviors, as their overall experience is likely to be more positive. Satisfaction can also affect perceived behavioral control by influencing individuals' beliefs about their ability to engage in environmental competence.

Satisfaction positively mediates the relationship between environmental commitment and environmentally responsible behavior (Ünal et al., 2018). This means that the positive effect of environmental commitment on environmentally responsible behavior is more substantial for tourists who were satisfied with their tourism experience. Therefore, Satisfaction can drive tourists to adopt environmentally responsible practices by fostering self-esteem and reducing cognitive dissonance.

In line with the independent variables presented, it is important to understand how are the dimensions of travel experiences influence the tourist's environmental competence of tourists in terms of environmental awareness and sustainable practice.

While several manifestations of environmental competence exist, waste recycling and waste management are generally considered crucial for environmental competence as they promote resource conservation and energy efficiency (Xia et al., 2022), recycling materials instead of extracting raw resources can reduce the strain on natural ecosystems and conserve valuable resources. Additionally, Al-Hajji, El-Haggar, and Abdelkareem (2021) explained that recycling often requires less energy than manufacturing products from scratch, leading to lower carbon emissions and reduced reliance on fossil fuels.

Proper waste management, including waste reduction, reuse, and recycling, helps minimize pollution, prevent landfill overflow, and protect the environment for future generations. Given these manifestations of environmental competence, the two components of environmental competencies used in this study still encapsulate the pursuit of empowering and protecting the finite natural resources, while letting tourist stay attuned for a clean and healthy tourist environment. These environmental competencies are covered in the paragraphs that follow.

On the one hand, environmental awareness, assesses tourists' knowledge and awareness of environmental issues and the potential influence of tourism on natural ecosystems and local communities. Here in environmental awareness, the study espouses that tourists with higher environmental awareness are more likely to have positive attitudes and intentions toward sustainable practices.

On the other hand, sustainable practice, measures the actual eco-friendly behaviors exhibited by tourists during their travels. It includes actions such as responsible waste disposal, water conservation, and support for local sustainable initiatives. According to the TPB, tourists with strong intentions and positive attitudes regarding sustainable practices are more likely to engage in such behaviors.

Considering these factors within the TPB framework, this research undertaking hopes to understand how perceived value, activity involvement, and satisfaction shape individuals' intentions and actions toward environmental competence.

Figure 1 illustrates the schematic diagram depicting the interplay between the identified variables in the study, offering a visual representation of the framework's implications.

Figure 1. Schematic Presentation of the Study

Research Objective

This study investigate the relationship between tourists' experiences and their environmental competence, emphasizing the importance of understanding how aspects such as perceived value and satisfaction affect tourists' awareness and practice of sustainable behaviors. This understanding is vital for promoting sustainable tourism and aiding industry stakeholders in developing strategies for responsible tourism that minimizes environmental harm.

METHODOLOGY

This study employs quantitative research, specifically the descriptive-correlational research design. Quantitative research is a research strategy that focuses on quantifying data collection and analysis. Creswell (2014) emphasized that the said design is based on a deductive method emphasizing theory testing, influenced by empiricist and positivist philosophies. Descriptive research describes the features of a population or phenomenon being examined. It does not answer how/when/why the qualities arose. Instead, it answers the "what" question. The researcher will employ a correlational research design in this investigation. The correlational research design of this study intends to use statistical data to determine the level of relationship between independent variables: Tourist Travel Experience Dimensions: perceived value and satisfaction to dependent variables: Environmental Competence.

The researcher will select 100 participants who have visited Secret Adventure Park, qualifying them for the study at no cost to answer the survey. Providing compensation or reimbursement to research participants is a standard practice to promote fairness and remove financial or logistical barriers. The compensation policy should align with ethical principles and budget constraints, ensuring participants are fully informed. Researchers should consult with their institution's ethics committee to ensure compliance with guidelines. Participants for this study will be chosen through purposive sampling, a non-

probability method effective for quick specific samples. Sample size refers to the number of subjects' representative of the population. Informed consent is crucial, ensuring participants understand the study's purpose and risks. Privacy concerns may arise due to data collection on travel experiences and environmental competence, requiring researchers to safeguard privacy. Participation may involve time and effort, potentially seen as burdensome, with tasks triggering emotional responses. Participants can contribute to knowledge in tourism and environmental competence, enhancing self-awareness and promoting sustainable practices. Compensation, incentives, or rewards may be provided, and participants often have access to study findings upon publication, offering insights into outcomes.

The researcher adapted a questionnaire of Bhutto et al. (2020) developed as the main data-gathering instrument to obtain the needed information effectively and efficiently. The researcher will provide a descriptive and organized system of gathering the data for the study. The questionnaire will use a Likert scale to assess opinions and attitudes; participants will be asked to choose the best answer for each statement using a five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 2 =disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree, 5 =strongly agree).

The research instruments will undergo content validation by the panel members and experts in the field. Their comments and suggestions will be sought; they will then be integrated into the final questionnaire. After the integration, it will be pilot tested to at least 30 park guests. Then, the internal consistency and reliability of the test will be determined using Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient. Cronbach's alpha provides the measure of the consistency of a test which is expressed as a number between 0 and 1.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. *Presents the Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of Participants' Assessment of Their Tourist Travel Experience (Perceived Value)*

Range	Description	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	19	19.0
3.51-4.50	High	58	58.0
2.51-3.50	Moderate	22	22.0
1.51-2.50	Low	0	0.0
1.00-1.50	Very Low	1	1.0
Total		100	100.0
Overall Mean		3.95	
Interpretation		High	
SD		0.61	

The overall mean value of 3.95 indicates a "high" perceived value among participants, indicating a favorable perception of their travel experiences. This means

that perceptions of social desirability may influence the perceived value of tourism products/services, emphasizing the significance of addressing social desirability and reputation enhancement in tourism marketing strategies.

Table 2. *Presents the Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of Participants' Assessment of Their Tourist Travel Experience (Satisfaction)*

Range	Description	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	18	18.0
3.51-4.50	High	66	66.0
2.51-3.50	Moderate	15	15.0
1.51-2.50	Low	1	1.0
1.00-1.50	Very Low	0	0.0
Total		100	100.0
Overall Mean			3.95
Interpretation			High
SD			0.55

The overall mean value of 3.95 indicates a “high” level of satisfaction among participants. The high level of satisfaction indicated by the tourists is likely due to the product and service meeting or exceeding expectations, offering good value for the price, and being deemed of high quality. It entails the significance of prioritizing these aspects to enhance overall traveler satisfaction.

Table 3. *Presents the Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of Participants' Level of Tourist Environmental Competencies (Environmental Awareness)*

Range	Description	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	23	23.0
3.51-4.50	High	64	64.0
2.51-3.50	Moderate	11	11.0
1.51-2.50	Low	1	1.0
1.00-1.50	Very Low	1	1.0
Total		100	100.0
Overall Mean			3.98
Interpretation			High
SD			0.62

The overall mean score for environmental awareness was 3.98, indicating a “high” level of awareness among participants. This finding suggests that participants are environmentally conscious and aware of global environmental issues. The implications of this result emphasize the need for tourism businesses to incorporate sustainable

practices and environmental conservation efforts into their operations to align with the values and concerns of their customers.

Table 4. *Presents the Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of Participants' Level of Tourist Environmental Competencies (Sustainable Practice)*

Range	Description	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	14	14.0
3.51-4.50	High	58	58.0
2.51-3.50	Moderate	27	27.0
1.51-2.50	Low	0	0.0
1.00-1.50	Very Low	1	1.0
Total		100	100.0
Overall Mean		3.91	
Interpretation		High	
SD		0.61	

Findings reveal that the participants rated their travel experience as generally “high”, as indicated by the overall mean of 3.91. This implies that the participants were overall engaged in sustainable practices during their travels, which can be attributed to their awareness of environmental issues and the importance of sustainable tourism. This can be achieved through educational programs, promotional campaigns, and partnerships with local waste management agencies.

Table 5. *Presents the Relationship between Tourist Travel Experience and Environmental Competence*

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.354	.287		1.23	.221
Perceived Value	.467	.084	.479	5.53**	.000
Satisfaction	.431	.095	.393	4.54**	.000

Model Summary

R = .810 R² = .657 Adj R² = .649 F = 92.47** p = .000

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 5 further shows the relationships between and among the variables of the study. The data revealed that tourist travel experience was found to be significantly related to environmental competence.

Among the specific components, perceived value came out as having the highest influence, indicating that for every unit increase in their assessment of perceived value of their experience, there is a corresponding 0.467 increase in their environmental competence ($B=.467$, $t=5.53$, $p = .000$). This suggests that when travelers perceive greater value in sustainable practices during their travels, they are more likely to develop higher environmental competence. This result is aligned on the environmental competence that attributed to other factors as a result in this study. Such factor include the nature of sustainable tourism and its influence on tourists' environmental behavior (Shen et al. (2016)). This further means that factors such as cultural background, personal values, and destination characteristics can also influence environmental competence among travelers. Furthermore, a study by Chen and Wu (2022) revealed that travelers who perceive a higher value in eco-friendly practices are more likely to adopt sustainable behaviors in their daily lives, thus contributing to a greater overall environmental competence. These findings collectively emphasize the significance of perceived value in promoting sustainable travel practices and fostering environmental competence among travelers.

Satisfaction also played a significant role in the participants' environmental competence, with a corresponding .431 increase in environmental competence for every unit increase in their assessment of satisfaction ($B=.431$, $t=4.54$, $p = .000$). This implies that satisfied travelers are more likely to exhibit higher environmental competence. Diaz and Mair's (2021) study on the relationship between customer satisfaction and sustainable tourism practices further supports this finding. The relationship between satisfaction and environmental competence among travelers is also reinforced in the study conducted by Gursoy et al. (2021), where they discovered that satisfaction with sustainable tourism experiences significantly contributes to the development of environmental competence among tourists. Additionally, a study by Chen and colleagues (2022) demonstrated that satisfaction with eco-friendly practices during travel positively influences travelers' environmental consciousness, which in turn, leads to higher environmental competence.

Conclusions

This study highlights the strong connection between participants' evaluations of their tourist travel experiences and their environmental competence, stressing the significance of promoting sustainable practices in the tourism sector. Aligned with the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), which focuses on influencing intention through attitude, perceived value, and satisfaction, enhancing perceived value and ensuring customer satisfaction with sustainable practices can effectively foster environmental competence among travelers. This approach holds potential in mitigating environmental impacts and encouraging responsible travel behavior.

The regression analysis affirms the substantial influence of perceived value and satisfaction on environmental competence, indicating that travelers who perceive higher value and satisfaction in their travel experiences tend to exhibit greater environmental awareness. These findings underscore the critical role of advocating for sustainable

practices within the tourism industry to nurture environmentally conscious behavior among travelers. Specifically, tourism enterprises should prioritize enhancing perceived value and ensuring customer satisfaction regarding sustainable practices to effectively nurture environmental competence among tourists.

In conclusion, these findings not only advance our understanding of the interplay between tourist experiences and environmental behaviors but also underscore the importance of sustainable tourism practices in addressing environmental impacts and promoting responsible travel behavior.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered that:

1. The owner/management may identify areas where participants' tourist travel experiences can be enhanced, such as improving products, services, and providing better information about sustainable practices, or offering additional amenities. The owner/management may also do the following:
 - 1.1 engage tourists by offering more variety of activities or customizing experiences to their preferences, and introduce to them more interactive or immersive options to increase their engagement;
 - 1.2 target the group of tourists with moderate environmental competency with educational programs and hands-on activities that promote sustainable practices to enhance their understanding and involvement in sustainable tourism.
 - 1.3 prioritize environmental conservation and sustainable development by implementing measures to reduce waste, conserve natural resources, and protect biodiversity.
 - 1.4 provide educational materials, guided tours, and opportunities for tourists that are in line with environmental conservation.
2. The tourists may actively participate in sustainable tourism practices by choosing eco-friendly accommodations, supporting local conservation efforts, and minimizing their environmental footprint during travel.
3. The future researchers may continue to explore the relationship between tourist experiences, environmental consciousness, and sustainable tourism practices. Identify effective strategies for promoting sustainable behaviors among tourists, evaluate the long-term impact of sustainable tourism initiatives, and explore innovative approaches to address emerging environmental challenges in the tourism industry.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to the conduct of this study, the researcher submitted the entire paper to the LC Research Ethics Committee team to determine if the present study merits the ethical standards of executing the study and if it conforms to the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

After obtaining a thorough review and approval from LC Research Ethics Committee, the researcher then sought approval and consent from the park management for the distribution of the research instrument to the tourist-participants. All personal data were collected for valid reasons. The researcher explained the study's risks and benefits to participants, who were informed of their voluntary participation and the confidentiality of data responses. The researcher also allowed participants to decline in answering the survey questionnaire at any time.

The handling of data collected after the completion of research is an important aspect of research ethics and should be carefully planned and communicated to participants. The data were stored securely to prevent unauthorized access, breaches, or loss. Access to data was limited to authorized personnel, such as the research team to ensure that data are not shared with individuals who do not have legitimate reason to access it.

When the data retention period expires, data would be securely disposed of to prevent any future access. To secure disposal, it may involve permanently deleting electronic files, shredding physical documents, or other appropriate methods. This is to make certain that participants have a clear understanding of the data handling process after the research is completed.

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